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CREATIVE ECONOMY AND DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES: THE PRESENT AND SCENARIOS OF THE FUTURE OF CITIES OF UKRAINE

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Abstract. The article is devoted to topical and urgent issues of the post-war reconstruction of Ukrainian cities as centers of economy, society, and culture. The prospects of involving scenario technologies and experience in the development of the creative economy, innovative designing, and digital technologies in solving the problems of the present and the future are considered. It has been proven that in Ukraine, the understanding of the importance of the creative industry in the issues of substantiating the specifics of the national model of the creative economy and the relevant management knowledge, updating and innovativeness of urbanism, forecasting and scenarios of the socio-economic development of territories and businesses is only being formed.

The key national economic interests in stimulating the creative economy by the cities of Ukraine are outlined. Scientifically oriented approaches to the definition and functional load of scenario procedures of the creative economy, such as: content-institutional, scenario-perspective, pragmatic-current ones, are given.

It has been proven that the support and science-based promotion of the creative sector in cities and territorial communities form the basis for stimulating the successful development of the national economy of Ukraine: the expansion of the middle class, the preservation of the potential of science and education, the reduction of unemployment, the inflow of investments, and the activation of informational and cultural progress. It is emphasized that the scenarios of the development of the creative economy in the cities of Ukraine can be considered as growth points. Peculiarities and directions of the post-war reconstruction of cities, taking into account the development of creative industries, are considered.

Groups of problems that can be solved by Ukrainian cities at the expense of scenarios for the development of the creative economy and its targeted management evaluation are presented. Emphasis is placed on the unique experience of the EU in supporting creative industries and the availability of not only positive assessments.

Keywords: creative management, information economy, cities, regions, post-war recovery.

Introduction

During the martial law in Ukraine, the issues of not just the optimal functioning of cities and their infrastructure, but also the definition and systematic discussion of the future in the context of compliance with the standards and best examples of the European Union (EU) become relevant. Modern problems, today's issues demand from the local authorities and the population of Ukrainian cities the need to quickly respond to various events of martial law, rapid management and security decisions, targeted involvement of innovative and digital technologies, which forms the accelerated implementation and use of relevant knowledge.

Today, any city of Ukraine, any local government must quickly, in fact instantly, resolve issues of security and elimination of the consequences of shelling, social and infrastructural support, restoration of networks and elimination of environmental threats, assistance to the military and other regions of the country. Information technologies and digital security in such conditions appear not only as a function of information and news, but also as elements of high-quality and

timely decision-making; accumulation of information and target databases; communication support and priority communication; increasing social responsibility and stability in "business-government-population" relations; support of economic complex in the format of continuous reproduction and timely supply of goods and services to the population, volunteers, the Armed Forces and military infrastructure; motivation of the population for security actions, preservation of the nation's intellectual capital; strengthening control over the fulfillment of a large number of requirements for the continuous supply of resources for the daily life of each family.

Under such conditions of a complex, unpredictable life, the issues of developing information about the future state of the economy, processes of evaluating urban shifts, updating the knowledge system on modeling society and economic complex, forming a holistic vision of scenario management in the extremely difficult conditions of today and the country's post-war recovery are not always considered relevant.

However, for the Ukrainian economy, the population of the country, the issues of vision of the future are not just urgent, they solve a large number of modern conflicts and prescribe options for the deployment of plans, events in an accelerated format of restoring life, which affects the processes of modern and perspective investment, ensuring the support of the world community, a new vision of urban success, the return of a significant part of the population from abroad. And one should not forget about the need to relieve social tensions, clearly position post-war progress in urban revival, eliminate the devastation of territories and inequality between the center and peripheral regions. It is impossible to allow the devastation of large territories of the Ukrainian East, post-war crisis phenomena in the urban plane of life reproduction.

The world is moving in the direction of expansion and targeted reproduction of the information economy and information society, digital progress and the accumulation of potential for managerial and social changes, improvement of the social environment of cities and modernization of production, systemic environmental control and the formation of a favorable business climate, creativity of ideas for the formation of scenarios of the future of territories. In such a movement, Ukraine must take its place, determine progressive shifts, both in the accumulation of knowledge and experience, and in their successful implementation into projects, real buildings, infrastructure facilities, the emergence of new neighborhoods and entire cities with comfortable living conditions.

Literature review

Issues of the future have always worried scientists, educators, leading authorities and corporate management, which is not just a professional interest, but also outlines the need to see changes, vectors of movement based not just on creative thoughts, but with elements of objective substantiation, bringing to the provisions of strategies, management measures. Scenarios of territorial development and modern projects of the future of cities are relevant at all times of human existence. In the context of world experience, the problems of modernity and determination of the prospects of urban development and progress are considered in the works of R. Florida (2019). It is in the works of this lecturer and scientist that the problems of modern cities of the world and especially the USA, regardless of their size and demographic status, but through the prism of the emergence of a creative class, a creative economy, the fluidity of poverty and the prosperity of the population in the conditions of deindustrialization of industrial regions, the destruction of production and the increase of potential sphere of services are systematically defined. The author's vision of the future of large and medium-sized cities is related to the prospects of information progress, the spread of digital technologies, trends in the industrial progress of large corporations and industries.

D. Hawkins (2001) outlined his contribution and conceptual vision, having initiated a systematic study of changes in the modern market economy of the world with a vector of rapid changes in relation to creative categories of the population, scenarios of states of the future in the concept

of a creative economy, where the basis is not ordinary material values, but first creative abilities and culture emerge.

The Ukrainian knowledge system of management and economics is gradually being enriched by research on the creative economy, as elements of the future of cities, businesses, social and innovative designing. The creative economy appears as one of the directions in the list of priority national economic interests in the system of prospects for the post-war recovery of our territory based on the best examples of Europe and America, Asia and China.

Scientists in the system of macro- and microeconomics, management, researchers of the M.I. Dolishnii Institute of Regional Studies of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine study the issues of theoretical substantiation of forecasts and scenarios for the development of the national economy, the role of creative vision, creative economy, emphasize the unique influence of established and selected models of the future on the development of territories, substantiate the mechanisms of building a creative economy in our country (Davymuka & Fedulova, 2017).

Successful integration of the processes of social progress with the determination of prospects for support, expanded reproduction of creative capital, creative class, as a strategic perspective for the development of Ukraine in the format of European values appears as a new direction of research in the knowledge economy. Such ideas belong to scientists Z. Pichkurova (2019) and S. Khanin (2022).

Particular attention should be paid to the publication of Ukrainian scientists I. Lytovchenko and V. Tomakh (2023), which is devoted to the prospects of the creative sector in the restoration of the economy and social sphere of our country. The authors not only emphasize positive assessments, but also form the basis for modeling processes in strategic planning of social and economic development of territories. The creative economy is considered as a concept of the post-industrial economy, a set of economic activities based on creativity, knowledge, technologies and innovations, which have a high potential for profitability and job creation. It has been proven that the formation of the creative economy is a natural result of social and economic development, which is associated with the recognition of the results of science as a direct productive force and a source of technological breakthroughs, an increase in the role of culture, the digital revolution and a significant level of promotion of social networks. The functioning of the creative economy promotes economic diversification, trade, innovations, the development of territorial communities; increasing the level of employment, social inclusion, reducing social tension, increasing public activities; national cultural identity; preservation of the environment, development of ecological consciousness.

The works of Yu. Kovalenko (2023) and O. Prygodiuk *et al.* (2023) as scientists who systematically form knowledge of regional information management, emphasize the problems of information asymmetry, imperfect information infrastructure, updated information culture and prove the perspective of strategic development of national economic interests in the conditions of global digitization, intensification of the implementation of digital technologies are of interest.

Scientists O. Zinchenko (2023), O. Prygodyuk (2023), and O. Finahina (2021) examine information progress and renewal of information infrastructure, changes in approaches to innovative information provision of regions, cities, and agglomerations based on knowledge management, creative ideas, and targeted digital technologies. The considered provisions not only enrich theoretical heritage, but also form management tools for the spread of innovative business, creative associations, clusters and networks in the regions of Ukraine.

Scientific achievements of D. Uzbek (2022), L. Pankova, and S. Milnichenko (2021) form a vision of national economic interests in the field of innovative-cluster, creative business breakthrough for the purpose of economic progress of the national economy of Ukraine in complex conditions of the globalized world.

Materials and methods

Research of the present and scenarios of the post-war future of Ukrainian cities in the format of expanding the sector of the creative economy, intensifying the involvement of digital technologies. Analysis of the world experience of development and recognition of the creative economy.

Results and discussion

Thanks to informational and innovative progress, humanity is moving at a frantic pace into the model of the knowledge economy, which is a real future, forming unique prospects for the development of informational progress and the spread of the creative economy sector. Scientists and managers are actively forming urban development scenarios based on the involvement of various knowledge, targeted management technologies of assessments and forecasting. The world scientific community actively reflects in its research the transition from the classical economy of cities, which was based on production and the service sector, to new forms of creative organization and fulfillment of economic activities.

Currently, Google, Apple, Facebook and other innovative developers have become the most powerful element of the knowledge infrastructure. They are examples of companies with the highest market capitalization. A radical turn towards knowledge capital is demonstrated by research by Ocean Tomo LLC: the share of intangible assets in the market value of companies increased from 17% in 1975 to 85% in 2015–2020 (Skyba, 2016).

The knowledge infrastructure, digital technologies, cultural and creative industries provide a change in the appearance and inner content of modern cities. Dynamic changes in the forms of population activities, innovative solutions in the organization of local space and business environment form the basis for attracting capital, management projects and creative people.

All this not only forms the outer shell, but also characterizes the transition to a new level of reproduction of society and economy on the platforms of intelligent, competitive management support for the development of the city. The creative economy and creative industry are becoming a prerequisite for the growth of the middle class, an expanded model of reproduction of the territory's population, and qualitative changes in image designing. It is the creative economy that has the prospect of becoming a real concept of the post-industrial, informational and innovative development of our country.

Therefore, continuous innovative progress, the essential role of human capital in the innovative development of the country; investments in new goods, services, technologies, human development; a large share of knowledge-intensive products in GDP; competition based on innovation; specialization and cooperation in the field of innovative activity of business entities; protection of intellectual property objects are considered to be the signs of a creative economy. The main factors of the growth of the creative economy include human potential; innovations; investment. The factors that ensure the development of the creative format of the economy include appropriate "soft" infrastructure (effective creative space), creative (and its varieties), innovative, investment, production and social management (Davymuka & Fedulova, 2017).

During the last decade, the creative economy, as stated by a group of experts of the World Economic Forum in Davos, is considered as a new growth model, which involves relatively small initial investments in "soft" infrastructure. Soft infrastructure is primarily knowledge infrastructure or human capital including institutions, ideas, cultural norms, concepts and solutions (Skyba, 2016). The creative economy is spreading, forming the accumulation of experience of functioning, first of all, as a new model of urban development, restoration of territories of various scales. For Ukraine, this is an invaluable experience, which should be embodied in real post-war reconstruction, management designing and image display, both of already existing locations of success, and the desired development scenarios of Kyiv and Kharkiv, Odesa and Dnipro, Chernihiv and Mariupol.

The European Commission published a report on the quality of life in European cities. Among the leaders were the western European cities of Zurich, Copenhagen and Groningen, and the lowest in the

ranking were the southern cities - Athens and Palermo. Kyiv was among the leaders in the rating of the most expensive cities in Europe, which is also significant in the problems of cities in our country and the recognition of asymmetry in the development of the national economy. The report included EU countries, candidates for joining the Union - Turkey, North Macedonia, Serbia and Montenegro, as well as Switzerland, Iceland, Great Britain and Norway. Residents of the cities of these countries were asked about the level of satisfaction in the following areas: inclusiveness, loneliness, employment, security, housing, environment, transport, culture, corruption and city services with elements of digital security. A minimum of 839 residents were interviewed in each city, and in total more than 71,000 interviews were conducted (Which cities in Europe, 2023; Ushkarenko *et al.*, 2018). According to the results of the survey, not only the understanding of the high quality of life in large European cities was clarified, but also the key problems were highlighted. Among them, the European community emphasized the conflicting conditions associated with the COVID-19 pandemic and immigrants from Ukraine in the areas of infrastructure provision, education, health care, and social communications. The burden on local authorities had increased many times, and not all issues had been resolved by the end of 2023 (Which cities in Europe, 2023).

Cities not only become centers of decision-making and concentration of population, government infrastructure and business, but also provide effective, gradual modeling of the future world, taking into account at the same time such complex processes as:

- taking into account the presence or absence of resource support;
- elimination of the challenges of urban problems and unplanned, unpredictable migration;
- increasing the uncontrolled potential of management and creative-oriented innovations, the transition to the targeted design of a creative environment and the corresponding economy (special manifestations on the examples of the tourism industry, recreational complexes, IT centers);
- formation of the latest standards of the business environment of an image nature and changes in cultural preferences (especially for young people and employees of the IT industry);
- innovative breakthroughs and targeted changes in construction, the combination of elements of environmental, energy, digital and socio-cultural renewal in this field and requirements for housing, infrastructural support.

A successful, developing metropolis uses innovative approaches, advanced digital technologies for the use of resources, their management in various areas. A creative metropolis is a space where residents can easily and quickly interact, develop in various areas, it is a space that promotes self-realization of citizens. This is facilitated by developed technologies, tolerant attitude towards each other, towards new ideas and thoughts. The modern metropolis is an attractive place to live, which provides ample opportunities for personal development. The space of the metropolis becomes the embodiment and personification of the modern way of life, worldview, while being the center of various opportunities for activity, saturation of social information, and cultural integration. Regardless of the size, current state or background of the modern metropolis, all of them are somehow doomed to find their own unique face. Cities compete with each other for human, information and money flows. Global connections and rivalry have partially descended from the level of nation states to the level of megacities (Pakulina *et al.*, 2019).

Ukraine still has a task ahead of it to take its place in the processes of forming a national model of the creative economy and relevant management knowledge specifically in the field of urban planning, forecasting and scenario of socio-economic development of territories and business. Let's list the key groups of problems that will be solved and have their own projection on decision-making in cities and territorial communities due to the involvement of forecasting and scenario technologies. Let's also immediately emphasize the management tools for the study of such conditions, which in itself will be a step to eliminate conflicts based on taking into account the assessments of specialists, professional diagnosis of the prerequisites for the occurrence of negative phenomena, risk zones.

We recommend to consider, study and eliminate the following groups of problems:

- ecological-recreational ones: a targeted survey and assessment of problem areas, identification and recording of contamination zones (both the consequences of war and pollution as a result of economic activities), crisis manifestations in restoring of recreation areas;
- economic ones: assessment of the prospects of stagnation or crisis phenomena in the economic complex, reduction of business activities, negative assessments of the business environment and investment attractiveness of the city. Determination, expert assessment of real economic interests of the government, business, population and the presence of a balance in socio-economic, informational, security development of the economic complex;
- social ones: assessment of the labor market and unemployment, the level of average wages in comparison with the capital or prosperous cities. Analysis of social infrastructure and its quality, education and culture;
- cultural and humanitarian ones: assessments of the potential of culture and its reflection in open access, creative industry and its potential, analysis of the activities of cultural institutions in the projection of future needs, availability and prospects of institutions for youth and children;
- institutional and legal ones: identification of gaps and shortcomings of regulatory provisions on digital security, involvement of new forms of cluster and network business, strategies and scenarios for the development of the creative economy;
- innovative ones: determination of priorities and prospects for renewal of production, evaluation of personnel training for innovation cluster and project management;
- cluster-business ones: assessment of business incubation and promotion of startups at various levels (education, local government, trade unions, business organizations), activities of small and medium-sized businesses. Assessment of the potential of cluster activities in the paradigm of relations "government-business-population-investors";
- urban-migratory ones: assessment of migration processes and features of population movement in the form of escape from poverty, social inequality and class division. Assessment of prospects for the return of the population from abroad, examination of the creative capital and professional assets of such immigrants;
- information and image ones: assessment of information potential (government, business, social organizations) and its creativity from the standpoint of promotion of creative industries, strategizing image and marketing measures for local production and cultural heritage.

The listed and briefly described groups of problems are closely intertwined and have a synergistic effect on each other. This is such a cocoon of problem areas that can be untangled only under conditions of targeted managerial influence on such processes and procedures. The following should be recognized as in demand: constant analysis and monitoring of problematic issues; understanding of movement vectors and the model being built within the borders of the country, region, city; availability of specialists in planning, scenario, innovation and cluster management; targeted involvement of artificial intelligence in complex issues of architecture, construction, taking into account the needs of future transportation.

In the management system, such a list of problems will be determined under the conditions of the need to assess individual sectors of the city's life (for example, transport, the sphere of entertainment and recreation). In the process of management designing, it is possible to single out major areas of management research - the innovative or project block. And at the same time, there is an option to consolidate research such as the "social-cultural-image" or "innovative-institutional-cluster-business" format.

The restoration of our country's economy should take place under the conditions of a joint scenario of the country's future in the paradigm of harmonious relations "government-population-business", as a territory of comfortable living of the population, a large multicultural family based on recognized, scientifically based principles and targeted approaches. As such approaches we recommend to recognize and, accordingly, disseminate: content-institutional; pragmatically current; scenario-prospective ones (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Scientifically oriented approaches to determining the functional load of scenario procedures

Source: compiled by the author

Support and science-based promotion of the creative sector forms the foundation for stimulating the national economy of Ukraine and the processes of expanded reproduction of economic complexes of cities, which can be considered as growth points in the scenario management of territorial development. One should expect, determine and study the peculiarities of post-war recovery, various changes in the following directions:

- intensification of cluster formation in the format of current European and world trends of targeted integration of resources;
- economic and social diversification of businesses, primarily small and medium ones;
- expansion of trade and changes in priorities in the organization of service provision;
- stimulation of the market of educational services and innovations;
- increase in environmental responsibility and implementation of innovative environmental projects;
- development of ecological culture, public control over the activities of harmful industries.

Let's briefly consider the classification of interests in stimulating the creative economy by the cities of Ukraine based on the principles of harmonious relations and innovative decision-making (Table 1). These are local interests, they are a reflection of the needs for development and progress of the local population, government, and business. Such a vision will be expanded through the ideas of the local community and on the platforms of appropriate resource provision.

Table 1. Classification of interests in stimulating the creative economy by cities of Ukraine

Classification feature	Groups of interests
1. Economy and expanded reproduction of the economic complex Economic interest	An increase in investments and the emergence of new areas of business activity. Integration of projects at the level of "state-foreign and domestic investors-local business-population" associations. Receipt of grants and prizes by business and the population
2. Social sphere Social interest	Involvement of resources in socially oriented projects, marketing and advertising activities Expansion of social business and its integration on platforms of openness with the population New forms of cooperation and creativity in the activities of authorities, educators, and business Expansion of the boundaries of social responsibility Receipt of grants and awards by business and the population

Table 1. Continued

3. Culture and education Social interest	Stimulation of cultural innovations, cluster formation with business and foreign investors Involvement of students and educators in the planning and implementation of business projects Increase in projects of creative presentation of information about the exclusivity of the city, its identity, tourist potential Self-realization of the population in decision-making regarding the development of creative businesses Receipt of grants and prizes by business and the population
4. Innovative sphere, smart specialization and digital progress Economic interest	Increase in innovative projects with elements of creative ideas Expansion of areas of smart specialization of small and medium-sized businesses Support of small businesses in the IT sector Intensification of creative technologies in the expanded range of smart services Stimulation of digital innovations Receipt of grants and prizes by business and the population
5. Development of small and medium-sized businesses, cluster formation Economic interest	Support of active cluster formation of small and medium-sized businesses, SMEs and large businesses in joint creative projects Intensification of business incubation Attraction of foreign investments in the development of SMEs Receipt of grants and prizes by business and the population
6. Ecology and recreation Social interest	Expansion of environmental audit zones in the format of social responsibility of business and population Development of creative projects for the development of recreation areas, nature protection measures Receipt of grants and prizes by business and the population
7. Image and information policy Information security interest	Formation of creative ideas, projects for the image display of the territory, events and business strategies, expansion of the potential of the city's image and information policy at the expense of creative projects of young people, writers, scientists and simply creative individuals Receipt of grants and prizes by business and the population

Source: compiled by the author

The creative sector of the economy, technologies and creative management projects should become a powerful source of reconstruction of the country after the war, ensure positive changes in the economy, social and cultural environment of cities. Expected management effects from targeted support, consistent scenario of changes in the economy of cities: increase in the level of employment; increase of the local budget; increase of the potential of small and medium entrepreneurship and social business; improvement of the image of the regions and the city; increase of public activities (primarily young people); strengthening of national cultural identity.

Conclusions

One should agree with the opinion that the creative economy and related industries are promising in the context of one of the sources of Ukraine's recovery. This is the real potential of attracting youth, IT specialists, management of the sphere of culture and tourism to cooperation in the conditions of the further development of the information society and the attraction of innovations.

However, it is not time to forget about negative evaluations, the problems in targeted production of the sector of the creative economy. Thus, the investors who stand on the positions of inefficiency in stimulating the sphere of entertainment, tourism and temporary pleasure have a negative attitude towards this sphere. The main comments are: excessive costs and management conflicts (in most cases, misunderstandings with the local population); impossibility of real control over project implementation; high risks of cultural conflicts; increase of manifestations of information asymmetry. This opinion is held by representatives of investment groups of big business, which have an orientation towards industrial progress, expansion of the spheres of influence of transnational capital and, in general, have a classic vision of the industrial future with elements of information and innovation progress.

In our opinion, it is necessary to take into account all opinions, evaluate the already gained experience of managing the creative sector, study both disadvantages and advantages. Special attention should be paid to the opinion of the mayors of the cities that have already become the centers of creative development of the EU - Barcelona, London, Berlin. And we should not forget about small cities that also already have positive evaluations in the rating system of European and world statistics - Malaga and Valencia (Spain), Brienz and Schwyz (Switzerland); Olomouc (Czech Republic); Trakai (Lithuania) and many others. This is a unique experience for our country in solving a large number of crisis problems, eliminating disparities in the development of small and large cities, accelerating informational progress and image revival.

Ukraine needs to accumulate relevant knowledge, form platforms, study such scientific, analytical, legal, journalistic, expert information under the conditions of its further preservation, elaboration, involvement in the development of scenarios for the development of cities, regions, territorial complexes, agglomerations, tourist centers and renewal of recreation centers, which will form the potential of scenarios and planning of optimal measures, digital technologies, business stimulation mechanisms.

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Conflict of interest

None.

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КРЕАТИВНА ЕКОНОМІКА ТА ДІДЖИТАЛ-ТЕХНОЛОГІЇ: СЬОГОДЕННЯ ТА СЦЕНАРІЇ МАЙБУТНЬОГО МІСТ УКРАЇНИ

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Анотація. Статтю присвячено актуальним і нагальним питанням повоєнного відновлення міст України як центрів економіки, соціуму, культури. Розглянуто перспективи залучення технологій сценарування та досвіду розвитку креативної економіки, інноваційного проектування, діджитал-технологій у вирішенні проблем сьогодення та майбутнього. Доведено, що в Україні лише формується розуміння значущості креативної індустрії в питаннях обґрунтування специфіки національної моделі креативної економіки і відповідних знань менеджменту, оновлення й інноваційності урбаністики, прогнозування та сценарування соціально-економічного розвитку територій та бізнесів.

Окреслено ключові національні економічні інтереси у стимулюванні креативної економіки містами України. Наведено науково орієнтовані підходи до визначення, функціонального навантаження процедур сценарування креативної економіки: змістовно-інституційні, сценарно-перспективні, прагматично-поточні.

Доведено, що підтримка та науково обґрунтоване просування креативного сектору в містах і територіальних громадах формує основу для стимулювання успішного розвитку національної економіки України: розширення прошарку середнього класу, збереження потенціалу науки та освіти, скорочення безробіття, припливу інвестицій, активізації інформаційного та культурного прогресу. Зроблено наголос, що саме сценарії розвитку креативної економіки в містах України можуть розглядатися як точки зростання. Розглянуто особливості та напрями повоєнного відновлення міст, зважаючи на розвиток креативних індустрій.

Наведено групи проблем, які можуть вирішувати українські міста за рахунок сценарування розвитку креативної економіки, її цільового управлінського оцінювання. Зроблено наголос на унікальному досвіді ЄС в питаннях підтримки креативних індустрій та наявності не лише позитивних оцінок.

Ключові слова: креативний менеджмент, інформаційна економіка, міста, регіони, повоєнне відновлення.